

The Influence of Student Motivation on Career Interests in the Field of Taxation

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ABSTRACT

The need for a motivation to encourage students majoring in career accounting, especially in the field of taxation, is discussed in this research. The research aims to find out the influence of career motivation, economic motivation, and social motivation on students' interest in a career in taxation. Quantitative research method with research type used is explanatory research. This study examined the relationship between student perception and motivation with a career interest in taxation. The population of this research data is a student majoring in accounting faculty of economics and business class of 2017 at the State University of Malang. The results of this study based on the hypothesis is H1: Student career motivation has a positive influence on career interests in the field of taxation there is a significant influence. H2: Student economic motivation has a positive effect on career interests in the field of taxation does not have a significant impact. H3: Student social motivation has a positive effect on career interests in the field of taxation has no significant effect.

1. INTRODUCTION

The world of education plays a very important role in improving the quality of human resources, because education is the environment in which the process of forming a profession takes place through the teaching and learning process (Miqdad et al. 2020). One of the study programs that are in great demand by students in higher education is accounting (Dewi and Setiawanta 2014).

Reasons why students choose accounting courses include promising future job prospects, economic improvement, and community appreciation (Ismail, A, and B 2012). In accounting courses, there are many courses that must be taken by students, one of which is taxation course (Wardhani et al. 2020). Many students think that working in the field of taxation is complicated, because of the frequent changes in regulations and calculation of taxation (Dewi

and Setiawanta 2014). The lack of knowledge of students who only get theory from lectures is not a practice that causes them to think so (Dayshandi, Handayani, and Yaningwati 2015). Therefore, a motivation is needed to encourage students to have a career, especially in the field of taxation (Kusumaningtyas 2013).

There are several factors that influence students' interest in career selection including economic motivation, career motivation and social motivation (Wahyuni, Purnamawati, and Sinarwati 2017). According to (Sarjono 2011), quality motivation is defined as an encouragement arising from one's self to improve the quality of one's self and ability in the field that is pursued so that it can carry out the task properly and correctly.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES

Motivation Theory

According to Siagian (2011), motivation is the driving force that results in a member of the organization willing and willing to exert skills in the form of skill or skill and time to organize various activities that are his responsibility and fulfill his obligations, in order to achieve the goals and various goals of the organization that have been predetermined.

This motivational theory explains the theory of basic human needs, if the basic needs have been met, then one will continue to be motivated to meet other needs with a higher level (Latifa 2015). This is in line with previous research which has found that motivation can influence a person's interest in choosing a career (Ferdianto, Tobing, and Barokah 2019). This theory is considered relevant and able to predict students' interest in the selection of their careers in the field of taxation (Amin 2020).

Hypothesis

1. Career Motivation
H1: Student career motivation has a positive effect on career interests in the field of taxation.
2. Economic Motivation
H2: Student economic motivation has a positive effect on career interests in the field of taxation.
3. Social Motivation
H3: Student social motivation has a positive effect on career interests in the field of taxation.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This research data uses quantitative research approach with the type of research used is explanatory research. This study examined the relationship between student perception and motivation with a career interest in taxation (Bektiarso, Setyanti, and ... 2021).

The target population in this study is all students majoring in accounting faculty of economics and business class of 2017 who are taking thesis at The State University of Malang. Students of the 2017 class are involved because they have already studied Tax Law, Taxation, Taxation Practicum and other courses so that students are considered to have enough knowledge about taxation and of course students of the 2017 class have thought about what career

they will pursue (Journal et al. 2020). In this study, the samples used were some of the accounting students of the Faculty of Economics and Business class of 2017 who were taking thesis at Malang State University numbering 120 students.

Data Collection

Research Data

Data collection used in this study was conducted by using the method of dissemination of questionnaires to obtain data on career interest in taxation towards the motivation of students majoring in accounting at the State University of Malang. Questionnaires were distributed to accounting students of Malang State University class of 2017 by spreading questionnaire links. A total of 33 statements were presented. Researchers tested independent variables in the study using a likert scale. The likert scale of the STS (Strongly Disagrees) with a score of one to the SS (Strongly Agreed) with a score of five.

Validity Test

This study used validity test used to measure whether or not a questionnaire is valid. A questionnaire is said to be valid if the question on the questionnaire is able to reveal something measured by the questionnaire.

Test the validity of this data calculated with SPSS program data. Criteria of acceptance: if r calculates $< r$ table then the questionnaire is invalid at alpha 0.05. Based on the validity test that has been done it turns out that the question in the research instrument is declared valid, the calculation of Validity Test with the help of SPSS.

Reliability Test

If the measuring instrument is valid, the next step is to test the reliability of the data. A questionnaire is said to be reliable or reliable when a person's answer to the question is consistent or stable over time. This study used Cronbach's Alpha statistical test to measure the reliability of research instruments where the significance level of 0.05 or 5%, in general reliability of less than 0.6 is considered poor and getting closer to the reliability coefficient of 1.0 is considered reliable (Siregar 2013).

Research Data Analysis

The following steps were taken in this study to test whether there was any influence

between the variables tested. Before performing multiple linear regression analysis, this study used a classic assumption test as a condition to know the data was worth testing, which consisted of:

Normality Test

Normality test is done with graph analysis that shows that the data used is normal distribution, to test residual normality by detecting normality is to look at the distribution of variable variables to be studied and tested statistically would be better if all variables distributed normally (Sunnyoto 2011).

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test aims to test whether in the research equation model there is a high or perfect correlation between free (independent) variables. A good regression model should not result in correlation between independent variables. If independent variables are correlated, then these variables are not original. An original variable is an independent variable whose correlation value among independent variables equals zero (Ghozali 2011).

To detect the presence of multicollinearity, can be seen from Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). If the VIF > 10, then multicollinearity occurs and vice versa (Sunnyoto 2011). Multicollinearity tests are used to test regression models with the discovery of correlations between independent variables.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in the regression model there is variance inequality from residual one observation to another. If the variance of one residual observation to another remains, it is called homocedasticity and if different is called heteroscedasticity.

A good regression model is homocedasticity or no heteroscedasticity (Ghozali 2011). Heteroscedasticity test can be done with Glejser test. The Glejser test, conducted by regressing residual absolute values against independent variables. If the significance value of each independent variable is more than 0.05 (sig > 0.05), then there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity. Conversely, if the significance value is less than 0.05 (sig < 0.05), then symptoms of heteroscedasticity occur.

Furthermore, after meeting the criteria on the classic assumption test, the stages in processing the data using linear regression are multiple.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression research was used to test hypotheses namely H1, H2, H3, and H4. If applied in the form of equations, then the model of multiple linear regression equations from this study is as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + b_4 X_4 + e$$

Description:

Y	= Career interest in taxation
A	= Constant value
b ₁ b ₂ b ₃ b ₄	= Regression coefficient
X ₁	= Career Motivation
X ₂	= Economic Motivation
X ₃	= Social Motivation
E	= Error factor (Standard Error)

Simultaneous Test (F Test)

Simultaneous testing (F) is used to determine the effect of independent variables on overall or simultaneous dependent variables. F test results can be seen in the ANOVA table with the significance level used is 5%. The test criteria used is if the p-value value > α, then H₀ is rejected while if the p-value value < α, then H₀ will be accepted. H₀ rejection means that simultaneously and significantly does not affect dependent variables. However, if H₀ is accepted, it means that independent variables simultaneously and significantly affect dependent variables.

Partial Test (T Test)

A partial test or t test aims to see the significance of individually independent variables' influence on dependent variables by assuming other variables are constant. T test serves to know the most dominant influence between each independent variable to explain the dependent variable with the level of significance used that is 5%. The test criteria used as that is if the value p value > α, then H₀ is rejected while if the value p value < α, then H₀ will be accepted. H₀ rejection means there is no significant influence between each free variable against the bound variable. However if H₀ is accepted then it can be said that there is an influence between free variables on partially bound variables.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Research Description

The following is the data of respondents in filling out a questionnaire which includes some information, among others:

No.	Career Options	Total	Percentage
1	Employee of the Directorate General of Taxation	38	38
2	Tax Consultants	35	35
3	Tax Specialist (Company)	27	27
Total		100	100%

Figure 1. Career selection in taxation

Figure 1 above shows that 38 respondents chose a career as an Employee of the Directorate General of Taxation with a percentage of 38%, 27 respondents chose a career as a Tax Specialist in the Company with a percentage of 27%, and 35 respondents chose a career as a Tax Consultant with a percentage of 35%. The following statistical description results of each variable studied, among others:

		Statistics			
		Motivasi Karir	Motivasi Ekonomi	Motivasi Sosial	Minat Karir Perpajakan
N	Valid	100	100	100	100
	Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean		41,00	34,91	16,91	21,65
Std. Deviation		3,779	4,708	1,928	2,176
Minimum		29	22	7	16
Maximum		50	45	20	25

Figure 2. Descriptive Statistical Results

Figure 2 explains that career motivation has the highest average score. This shows that the motivation in the career level in accounting students at State University of Malang towards career interests in the field of taxation is very high compared to other motivations.

Data Analysis

Classic Assumption Test

This study used classic assumption tests to find out how free variables affect bound variables and to find out whether multiple linear regression models are feasible or not. The classic assumption regression used consists of:

Normality Test

This study used normality test used is Kolmogorov Smirnov. Normality test results in this study are:

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		100
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	,0000000
	Std. Deviation	1,78499162
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,056
	Positive	,045
	Negative	-,056
Test Statistic		,056
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,200 ^{c,d}

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.

d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

Figure 3. Normality Test Result

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test results contained in the following table show for all variables have a tolerance of more than 0.10 and VIF less than 10, so it can be said that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity.

		Collinearity Statistics	
Model		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Motivasi Karir	,863	1,159
	Motivasi Ekonomi	,858	1,166
	Motivasi Sosial	,818	1,223

a. Dependent Variable: Minat

Figure 4. Multicollinearity Test Result

Heteroscedasticity Test

Here are the results of heteroscedasticity testing that has been done in this study.

Figure 5. Heteroscedasticity Test Result

When viewed in scatterplot images, normal distributed data is seen after glejser test.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis aims to determine whether or not there is a significant influence between two or more free variables (X1, X2, and X3) on bound variables (Y) (Ghozali 2011).

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	9,561	2,300		4,156	,000
Motivasi Karir	-,006	,052	-,011	-,118	,906
Motivasi Ekonomi	,167	,042	,361	3,991	,000
Motivasi Sosial	,386	,104	,342	3,691	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Minat Kerja Perpajakan

Figure 6. Multicollinearity Test Result

Figure 6 shows that the models of multiple linear regression equations are as follows:

$$Y = 9,561 + (-0.006)X_1 + 0.167X_2 + 0.386X_3 + e$$

From the equation of linear regression model above, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Constant score of 9,561 states that independent variables (career motivation, economic motivation, and social motivation) are constant, student interest is 9,561.
2. The value of the regression coefficient of career motivation variable (X1) is -0.006 and marked negatively indicates that the career motivation variable has a relationship that is not in line with the interest for a career in taxation. This means that any inconsistent influence on career motivation of one unit then the interest for a career in taxation is 0.006 assuming that other free variables are of fixed or constant value.
3. The value of the regression coefficient of economic motivation variable (X2) is 0.167 and marked positively indicates that the economic motivation variable has a direct relationship with the interest for a career in taxation. This means that any increase in economic motivation by one unit of interest for a career in taxation is 0.167 assuming that other free variables are of fixed or constant value.
4. The value of the regression coefficient of Social Motivation variable (X3) is 0.386 and marked positively indicates that the social motivation variable has a direct relationship with the interest for a career in taxation. This means that any increase in social motivation by one unit of interest for 25 careers in

taxation is 0.386 assuming that other free variables are of fixed or constant value.

Hypothesis Test

F Test Significance Results

To find out the test results of simultaneous significance can be seen in the following table:

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	153,317	3	51,106	15,554	,000 ^b
	Residual	315,433	96	3,286		
	Total	468,750	99			

a. Dependent Variable: Minat Kerja Perpajakan

b. Predictors: (Constant), Motivasi Sosial, Motivasi Karir, Motivasi Ekonomi

Figure 7. F Test Significance Results

Based on the results of simultaneous significance test (test F) it is known that the research model on career interest in the field of taxation is influenced by quality motivation, career motivation, economic motivation, and social motivation with significant value gain of < 0.05, then free variables (quality motivation, career motivation, economic motivation, and social motivation) have a significant effect on bound variables (career interest in taxation) in accounting students of Malang State University class of 2017.

T Test Significance Results

Partial significance tests are used to assess how far the influence of individual independent variables can be in dependent variable variations. Based on figure 7, the results of the partial significance test (t test) are as follows:

1. Career motivation has a significance value of 0.906 (more than 5%) which means that H0 is rejected or H1 is acceptable, so partially career motivation has a significant positive effect on career interest in taxation in accounting students of Malang State University class of 2017.
2. Economic motivation has a signification value of 0.000 (less than 5%) which means that H0 is rejected or H2 cannot be rejected, so partially economic motivation has a significant positive effect on the interest of a career in taxation in accounting students of Malang State University class of 2017.
3. Social motivation has a significance value of 0.000 (less than 5%) which means that H0 is rejected or H3 cannot be rejected, so

partially social motivation has a significant positive effect on the interest of a career in taxation in accounting students of Malang State University class of 2017.

Discussion

The Influence of Career Motivation on Career Interests in the Field of Taxation

The results of this study showed that career motivation variables have a positive effect on career interests in the field of taxation (Paramita et al. 2020). Career motivation has an important role in the interest of career in the field of tax (Park 2017). If career motivation increases, then the interest of students for a career in taxation will also increase (Journal et al. 2020).

In this study, most of the career motivations of accounting students of Malang State University influenced the interest in a career in taxation (Jamil, Titisari, and Suryaningsih 2020). This can be seen based on the respondent's average answer to his statement of career motivation is very agreeable. High career motivation sometimes a person wants an increase in skills for the development of a career (Ismail et al. 2012). If a person does not have a high motivation when he wants to achieve a certain goal both in choosing a career and in other things, then that goal will not be achieved to the maximum (P Titisari, Afandi, and Lukiyanto 2020). Therefore, it takes a high motivation in an achievement to be intended (Abdillah 2011). Therefore, it explains that a person's career motivation can influence his/her interest in choosing a career (Hakim, Tobing, and Istifadah 2019).

The Influence of Economic Motivation on Career Interests in the Field of Taxation

The results of this study showed that economic motivation has a positive effect on the interest of students in the field of taxation which means the higher the economic motivation in a student, the greater his interest in a career in taxation and vice versa, the lower the interest of students, the less interest in a career in taxation.

In this study, most of the economic motivation of accounting students of Malang State University influenced the interest in a career in taxation. This can be seen based on the respondent's average answer to his statement of economic motivation is to agree. High economic motivation sometimes a person wants the implementation of the salary received and the

facilities provided in a job (Dewi and Setiawanta 2014). If a person does not have a high motivation when he wants to achieve a certain goal both in choosing a career and in other things, then that goal will not be achieved to the maximum (Bektiarso et al. 2021). Therefore, it takes a high motivation in an achievement to be intended (Suhadi, Titisari, and Setyanti 2019).

The Influence of Social Motivation on Career Interests in the Field of Taxation

The results of this study showed that social motivation variables have a positive effect on career interests in the field of taxation (Mudawiyah, Prihatini, and Wulandari 2019). Social motivation has an important role in the interest of careers in the field of tax. If social motivation increases, then the interest of students for a career in taxation will also increase (Wardayati et al. 2019).

In this study, most of the social motivation of accounting students of Malang State University influenced the interest in a career in taxation (Soni Wirawan 2019). This can be seen based on the respondent's average answer to his statement of social motivation is to agree. High social motivation sometimes a person wants the praise given by others to his work (Indrawati 2009). If a person does not have a high motivation when he/she wants to achieve a certain goal both in choosing a career and in other things, then that goal will not be achieved to the maximum (Wahyuni et al. 2017). Therefore, it takes a high motivation in an achievement to be intended (Id 2019). Therefore, it explains that a person's social motivations can influence his or her interest in choosing a career (Purnamie Titisari, Susanto, and Swastika 2020).

5. CONCLUSION, SUGGESTION, AND LIMITATIONS

Conclusion

This research focuses on the influence of quality motivation, career motivation, economic motivation, and social motivation on career interests in the field of taxation in students majoring in accounting Malang State University class of 2017. Based on the tests that have been done, there are four conclusions.

First, career motivation has a positive effect on career interests in the field of taxation. This research is consistent with previous research that found that when students have high career motivation, the higher the interest of accounting

students of Malang State University for a career in taxation. This result is also in accordance with the fifth hierarchy in the theory of needs put forward by Maslow, namely self-actualization, because it is normal if in the career, one wants the potential that the person has developed to the maximum so that it can be an optimal and effective ability. Therefore, for students majoring in accounting, this research can be used as a reference for consideration in the field of taxation and know some information about the field of taxation.

Second, economic motivation has a positive effect on career interests in the field of taxation. This research is consistent with previous research that found that a person will be interested in choosing to pursue a career in taxation, because if working in the field of taxation of course the salary he earns is quite large than working in other fields. In addition, this result is also in accordance with the motivation theory described by Herzberg that the system of wages and salaries and financial rewards are several types of factors that are factors that please workers or extrinsic factors that influence people to work. The more students have a high economic motivation, the higher the interest of accounting students of Malang State University for a career in taxation. Therefore, for students majoring in accounting, this research can be used as a reference for consideration in the field of taxation and know some information about the field of taxation.

Third, social motivation has a positive effect on career interests in the field of taxation. This research is consistent with previous research which found that the existence of socialization or encouragement from various parties, he will be motivated himself to establish which career choices he will choose. While students have high social motivation, the higher the interest of accounting students of Malang State University for a career in taxation. Therefore, for students majoring in accounting, this research can be used as a reference for consideration in the field of taxation and know some information about the field of taxation.

Limitations and Suggestions

Limitations in this research is that this research is only done in accounting students of Malang State University, while in order to make the results more accurate the next research is recommended to increase the scope of research by examining accounting students from other

universities. In addition, further research is also recommended to add careers in other accounting fields such as public accountants, government accountants, and educator accountants.

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